

Two design cases exploring development of social emotional learning solutions

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Abstract This paper explores the development of social emotional learning (SEL) solutions created by two design teams. Both teams combined methods from design thinking, empathetic design, rapid prototyping, and evidence-based prevention to answer the complex question: *How might we support social and emotional development in young children (ages 3-6)?* The two teams approached the problem in the same way, but varied the environment of the end-users between homes and childcare centers. The purpose of this paper is to reflect on the two distinct design cases and indicate noteworthy characteristics from them. In particular, we hope to increase and encourage the translation of evidence-based research into real world solutions.

Keywords *Design thinking, Empathy, Prototyping, Social innovation, Social-emotional learning*

Introduction & design project background

Supporting early social emotional learning (SEL), particularly for vulnerable children and their families, is essential for improving the health and quality of life in all communities (Jones et al., 2015). However, conventional methods to translate evidence-based SEL interventions into real world contexts have had limited impact (Rotheram-Borus et al., 2012). The Robert Wood Johnson Foundation (RWJF), recognized the opportunity to develop innovative solutions in this design space, and funded this research design project to solve this need.

Our project began with the following frame: How might we support social and emotional development in young children (ages 3-6)? We were given four months to solve this challenge. This project took place in two locations in the US: Colorado and Pennsylvania. Each location supported their own small design team consisting of 5-8 members. Team members had diverse backgrounds spanning from early education, learning sciences, mechanical engineering, human-computer interaction, and human development and family studies.

It was recognized that the varied routines children experience at home and at childcare centers become a critical part of children's lives and serve as opportunities for skill, knowledge, and behavior development, such as SEL competencies (Greenberg, 2006). Due to the open-ended nature of the problem, the teams decided to explore in these two different end-user contexts: homes and childcare centers. In Colorado, the team approached the problem in the home environment, while the Pennsylvania team focused on childcare centers.

In this paper, we present insights and reflections from the development of these two solutions. This paper will proceed as follows: first, we present background

on the project, followed by the specific designs developed by the two design teams. Finally, we end with a discussion of the noteworthy characteristics from the design cases and the opportunity to translate evidence-based research into scalable, commercially available tools or products.

Colorado design team: solution for home environment

The Colorado team started by observing users in both childcare centers and home environments. After extensive empathic observations, the team discovered that a child's day is comprised of a series of transitions with a significant one being the transition between childcare and home. The childcare centers provide immense structure to the children's day. However, this structure often breaks down once the child is at home. Because of this insight, the team decided to focus on the home environment for the context of the design problem.

This first stage of the design thinking process is empathizing, which entails gaining insights about the experiences, challenges, and behaviors of the children and families. To aid in synthesizing our observations and interviews, the team used the five core competencies of social-emotional learning (Figure 1, www.casel.org, 2015): self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making. When mapping insights to these competencies, we learned that children were often not given the chance to strengthen self-awareness of their emotions. This helped lead us into our re-defined problem statement moving forward: *How might we increase children's self-awareness of their emotions during transition periods throughout the entire day?*

Moving from problem definition to ideation, the team used many techniques to encourage idea formation.

Figure 1. CASEL's Five Core Competencies of Social Emotional Learning (www.casel.org, 2015).

Ultimately, we narrowed down to three top solutions and rapidly prototyped them (Figure 2). These ideas were (1) a handheld feelings and activity wheel, (2) a combination of a feelings poster, writing prompts, and self-reflection, and (3) a feelings embodiment of emotions activity (yoga-influenced). We immediately brought these simple prototypes to our users and gained valuable feedback to move the design forward. We combined these insights, which allowed us to move forward to the next phase of prototyping a fully functioning design.

In the functional prototyping phase, we developed a hand-held "feelings, activities, and transition toy" (Figure 3). The purpose of this toy was (1) to be standalone for children to use on their own, (2) to encourage awareness of emotions through use the mirror and pictures of children's faces, (3) and to support emotionally-hard transitions in a child's day (like bedtime) by identifying these transitions and matching supporting activities with them. We created

three versions of the same design to test user interaction design factors, such as motions (sliding, spinning, pulling), prompting words and pictures, and placement of activities, feelings, and transitions. We left these prototypes with our users for a week so that they could truly embed the design into their lives. After the week, we picked up the prototypes and collected feedback from the users through observations and interviews.

All of the user feedback was taken into consideration as we moved into our final prototype for the project. The most important user feedback included:

1. Creating multiple motions (flip, spin, pull, slide)
2. Specific placement of activities, transitions, and emotions
3. Incorporating audio/light prompting
4. Putting pictures next to all words
5. Ability to switch out words/pictures easily
6. Small, portable size
7. Focus on mirror and emotions
8. Bright fun colors with neutral base

Our final design (Figure 4) was a hand-held toy that helps children recognize their emotions as well as support the many emotionally-difficult transitions throughout their day. A key aspect to this design is that it can be child-led, eliminating additional burden on the parent. The main features are the mirror and pictures of children's faces related to specific emotions. This allows children to see the facial expressions and then look at themselves to see if this reflects their emotions. There is capability for audio and lighting prompts built into this design to help prompt the children to express and reflect on their emotions. The design is meant to be customizable in terms of transitions and supporting activities as shown by the hinged opening. This allows parents to exchange the spin-wheel of transitions in their day (i.e. dinner, bedtime, travel) and the sliding reel of activities to help support these transitions (i.e. sing a song, read a book, go for a walk).

Figure 2. Colorado Team Initial Simple Prototypes: Feeling + Activity Wheel (left), Feelings Posters, Writing Prompts, and Self Reflection (middle), Feelings Embodiment Activity (right).

Figure 3. Colorado Team Second Prototypes: three versions of feelings, activities, and transitions handheld toys (left) and testing with different user environments (right).

Pennsylvania design team: solution for childcare environment

The Pennsylvania team focused exclusively on childcare centers. This team followed the same design thinking process as Colorado: empathize with users, redefine the problem, ideate wild ideas, prototype realistic solutions, test solutions with users, and iterate where necessary. This project flow is mimicked in the following paragraphs as we provide a brief overview of the findings this team discovered at each stage.

At the start of the project, as the design team entered the empathy stage, experts in SEL and empathic observations provided team members with a brief background and tutorials. Findings from initial site visits led to insights that redirected the interview protocol and questions used in a second round of site visits. The second round of site visits provided the design team with deeper user stories and led to the problem statement: *How might we transform early learning centers into places where people, processes, and products are aligned to create, capture, and*

share “a-ha” moments, so that every child has a great day?

This new problem frame helped us move towards rapidly generating ideas. We identified that the large amount of biodiversity present in our samples would make single, stand-alone products difficult to transition across all markets. As a result, the PA team identified the need for a product platform that could be translated across the multitude of childcare center. A platform is a collection of common elements implemented across a range of products; platforms work best in contexts where there is a wide variety user groups, yet there exists common needs across user groups.

Our team identified three common elements across centers and user groups:

1. Teachers feel most fulfilled during a-ha moments with students, yet can occasionally miss a-ha moments or opportunities for these moments due to classroom and resource constraints

Figure 4. Colorado Team Final Prototype. Showing the feedback incorporated in the 3D rendering (left) and the handheld physical size (right).

Figure 5. Log-In Screen and Impact Dashboard of Proposed Digital Platform.

2. Teachers and parents across centers want to communicate effectively with one another, but time and schedule constraints make these periods difficult and stressful
3. All childcare centers have some formal check in and check out process

These common characteristics led our team to develop a platform focused on the check in and check out process because it occurred at every center and provided an opportunity to engage parents. The base platform was an RFID check in process that used check-in and check-out times as opportunities to incorporate SEL activities from evidence-based programs. Add-ons such as at home activities, classroom activities, point systems, and ways to incorporate other environments into an SEL program were explored in the second round of ideation. Our team prototyped a digital interface of the proposed platform system to show teachers and parents how the new check in process might work, and how data regarding SEL development could be collected and displayed in a teacher and parent dashboard. The creation of new SEL opportunities during what is typically a stressful time (checking in and out of centers), along with the dashboard of SEL development, and digital interface for an evidence based SEL program addressed the evolved “how might we question.” Figure 5 highlights the digital interface and dashboard components of our platform.

This solution, which integrates lessons from the fields of industrial design, electrical engineering, and human health and development would not have been created without the transdisciplinary team, design thinking tools, empathic design methods, and rapid prototyping. These factors combined with the fast paced nature of the project and the constant feedback from end users helped shape and guide the development of a truly unique solution that addressed the initial “how might we” statement.

Discussion and implications

This short paper reflected on two design teams as they solved the problem of increasing social emotional development in young children. We saw how the same complex problem can be addressed multiple ways by changing the context of the end-users, in this case between homes and childcare centers.

The biggest takeaway from these design projects was the ability to translate evidence-based social emotional learning interventions into real world solutions. Often, work in areas like SEL is researched and documented in academia, but not always translated into practice (Rotheram-Borusinter et al., 2012). We bridged this gap in our work, and hope to encourage others to do so as well.

We have synthesized five noteworthy reflections on how we were able translate research to practice in an attempt to encourage more researchers and designers to come together to decrease the time from discovery (intervention research) to impact (broad dissemination and use).

1. Form transdisciplinary teams that *combine* expertise from multiple domains to form new innovative solutions (Lawrence and Després, 2004). It is especially important to include both researchers and designers on the team.
2. Become familiar with both the state of the research in the field of study (like SEL and early childhood education in our case) as well as the best practices and tools to support the design teams.
3. Use a design thinking approach that emphasizes immersion into the design space environments as well as rapidly building and testing solutions with users (Grysiakab et al., 2011).
4. Define multiple user contexts as a means to think about the problem and solution in different, yet complementing ways.
5. Set an initial short timeline (like 4-6 months) to develop solutions as a way to get the team bias towards action compared to contemplative thinking.

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